

AK47 -- AUTOMATIC KALASHNIKOV-1947

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7904659>

Nasibjonov Nurillo Nasibjon ogly

Fargona State University

Faculty of Military Education

Abstract.

This weapon is a well-known symbol of the army of the Soviet Union. It was first used by the Soviet army under the name AK-47, but its world-famous name Kalashnikov came from the family of the gun maker.

Keywords.

AK 47, Automat, Kalashnikov, Weapon,

The weapon is named after him "Avtomat Kalashnikova 1947", abbreviated as AK-47. Since that day, the Soviet Army has adopted this weapon as its inseparable symbol. But the development and adaptation of the AK-47 to the army continued until 1959, when the modernized popular AK-47 was created. The entire Soviet army was armed with this weapon, and the communist neighbor China was allowed to produce it. This permission was later extended to the other 18 Warsaw Pact countries. Although the Kalashnikov was inspired by the Shtrumgever, its weight, ease of use, and speed were far superior to any automatic weapon produced up to that time. For example, if you compare the Strumgever with the AK-47, despite the fact that the main body is similar, the technology of the AK-47 is somewhat more complex and there are no flaws in its use. The fact that the bullet penetrates deeper into the target than other weapons is an important factor that has kept the AK-47 superior to other automatic weapons until now.[1]

The AK-47's durability, lightness, and low cost of production quickly spread it around the world. The role of Kalashnikov became very important in the armed conflicts caused by the "Cold War" of that time. All the countries that were part of the Soviet Union bought its licenses and produced millions of Kalashnikovs. This weapon quickly became a symbol of revolution and freedom uprisings in the world. Over the years, according to the demands of the world, several modernized and adapted to different geographical conditions were produced, as well as new models adapted to the inimitable 7.62 caliber bullet to the famous NATO 5.56 caliber bullets.

Today, the number of this weapon has become legendary, the total number of registered and produced Kalashnikov assault rifles is around 70-110 million. It is the most marketable weapon in the world. However, its founder did not receive any monetary reward for this invention. But thanks to the "gem" he created, thousands of factories in the world continue to make money. In 2007, Mikhail Kalashnikov stated that 9 out of 10 Kalashnikov assault rifles in the world are copies or fakes. In fact, only 10-12% of the currently produced Kalashnikov assault rifles are produced in Russia, and the remaining 90% are produced by other countries. There are mainly two reasons for this, the first is that during the Cold War, the Soviet Union allowed many countries to produce this weapon in order to strengthen its strategic partners. But now the Soviet Union itself does not exist, and the collapse of the Soviet Union was not taken into account in the agreements concluded with them. For this reason, most of these countries continue to produce AK-47 weapons. The 2nd reason is that after the collapse of the Soviet Union, the entire Soviet weapons arsenal was looted by former military personnel and sold cheaply to several countries, regardless of their ideological views. Also, due to the decrease in demand for weapons after the fall of the Communist bloc in the world and the deterioration of the socio-economic situation in the countries of the former Soviet Union, the price of this weapon fell to \$20 in the 90s. During this period, there is no information that the technologies related to the production of these weapons were also sold. In 2006, at the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe's Small Arms Forum in Vienna, Russia announced that it had lost control of the world's Kalashnikov production and that only 10% of them were produced in Russia.

REFERENS:

1. Ёигиталиева, З. М. (2020). МАТНДА МОДУСНИНГ ИФОДАЛАНИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. Международный журнал искусство слова, 3(2).
2. Yigitaliyeva, Z. (2020). EXPRESSION OF THE MODUS BY PARALINGUISTIC MEANS. Theoretical & Applied Science, (2), 25-29.
3. Rasulovna, K. M. (2023). TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES. INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022, 2(15), 64-67.
4. Abduvaliyeva, F. T., Azizova, F. L., Akromov, D. A., & Sherkuziyeva, G. F. (2022). APPROVAL AND ECOLOGICAL-HYGIENIC ASPECTS OF WATER SUPPLY TO POPULATION POINTS.

5. Кадирова, М. (2021). Педагогиканинг асосий категориялари, уларнинг тиббий таълим тизимидаги семантик мазмуни. Общество и инновации, 2(10/S), 52-57.
6. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK TARBIYASIDA MUZEYLARNING MUXIM AHAMIYATI. THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY, 1(4), 166-168.
7. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). YOSHLARNI VATANPARVARLIK RUXIDA TARBIYALASHDA URUSH VA MEHNAT FAXRIYLARI BILAN TEMATIK KECHA VA UCHRASHUVLAR O'TKAZISHNING MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI. SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS AND TRENDS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, 1(5), 123-125.
8. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). YOSHLARNI VATANPARVARLIK RUXIDA TARBIYALASHDA URUSH VA MEHNAT FAXRIYLARI BILAN TEMATIK KECHALAR VA UCHRASHUVLAR O'TKAZISHNING MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI. PEDAGOG, 1(4), 1340-1342.
9. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). O'SIB KELAYOTGAN YOSH AVLODGA HARBIY TEKNIKA TO'GARAKLARINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH VA ULAR BILAN A'MALIYOTDA TADBIQ ETISH. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 1(10), 141-143.
10. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). O 'QUVCHILAR HARBIY VATANPARVARLIK TARBIYASINING ASOSIY VAZIFALARI VA YO'NALISHLARI, HARBIY VATANPARVARLIK TARBIYASIDAGI SAMARADORLIKKA ERISHISH YO'LLARI. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(10), 186-189.
11. Xaydarali o'g'li, X. N., Komiljon o'g'li, Y. Q., Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S., & Saydaliyevich, U. S. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK MAVZUSIDA NAZARIY KONFERENSIYALAR TAYYORLASH VA O 'TKAZISH. INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS, 1(12), 107-111.
12. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). YOSHLAR ONGIDA MILLIY G'OYA VA MAFKURA TUSHUNCHALARI SHAKLLANTIRISH. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(4), 11-15.
13. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI O 'QUVCHI YOSHLARINI-O'ZBEKISTON XALQI VA QUROLI KUCHLARINING JANGOVAR VA MEHNAT AN'ANALARI ASOSIDAGI HARBIY-VATANPARVARLIK TARBIYASI". INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 1(12), 393-395.
14. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK MAVZUSIDAGI MA'RUZA, REFERATLAR TAYYORLASH VA UNGA

QO'YILGAN TALABLAR. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 3(25), 395-398.

15. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). YOSHLARNI VATANPARVARLIK RUXIDA TARBIYALASHDA JANGOVAR BAYROQQA VA HARBIY QASAMYODGA SODIQLIK HISSINI UYG'OTISH. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(18), 355-357.

16. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g, S. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK MAVZUSIDA NAZARIY KONFERENSIYALARNI MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(14), 1120-1121.

17. G'aniyevna, S. A. (2023). ISSUES OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND RECEPTION. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 3(28), 191-195.